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CONTENTS

COPYRIGHT ACT OF NIGERIA, 2023: AN APPRAISAL OF RIGHTS Ibrahim Danjuma_____	1
APPRAISAL OF THE CHALLENGES AND THE PROSPECT OF PROSECUTING CYBERCRIME IN NIGERIA Aminu Umar_____	21
A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON <i>SAHIFAT AL-MADINA</i> AND THE PRINCIPLES OF A MODERN CONSTITUTION VIS-À-VIS THE POSITION OF POLITICS UNDER ISLAMIC LAW Babayo Yakubu, Haruna Alhaji Garba, Waheedah Yunusa Muhammad_____	41
THE SCIENCE OF JUDICIAL PRECEDENTS AND THE CHAMELEONIC NATURE OF JUDICIAL DECISIONS IN POLITICAL MATTERS IN NIGERIA Antom Vanen Lawrence_____	58
AN EXAMINATION OF THE JURISDICTION AND COMPETENCE OF THE FEDERAL AND STATES HIGH COURTS OVER ISLAMIC BANKING DISPUTES IN NIGERIA Ibrahim Buhari Shehu_____	73
AN ASSESSMENT ON THE ADEQUACY OF PERSONAL INCOME TAX ACT IN NIGERIA Ahmad Aliyu_____	93
AN APPRAISAL OF THE APPLICATION OF THE AFRICAN CHARTER ON DEMOCRACY, ELECTIONS AND GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA Usman Sani, Salisu Abubakar_____	106
THE NIGERIAN JUVENILE JUSTICE SYSTEM: IMPLEMENTATION, CHALLENGES AND THE WAY FORWARD Aminu Umar_____	128
AN APPRAISAL OF THE TREATMENT AND CARE OF GUNSHOT VICTIMS ACT, 2017 Agbo Friday Ojonugwa, Mary Arthur-Jolasinmi_____	152
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR COMBATING DOMESTIC VIOLENCE IN BAUCHI STATE AND PLATEAU STATE Abubakar Adamu Garkuwa, Ibrahim Danjuma, PhD_____	162

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR COMBATING DOMESTIC VIOLENCE IN BAUCHI STATE AND PLATEAU STATE

By

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ABSTRACT

The issue of domestic violence and the efficiency of the framework put in place to combat domestic violence has gained prominent attention in international discourses in recent times. This paper compares the relevant provisions of the Violence Against Persons (Prohibition) Laws of both Bauchi and Plateau State being one of the legal frameworks for combating domestic violence in the states with a view to identifying their strengths and weaknesses. The paper argues that Society and individuals are two inseparable units of human existence and in the course of survival within the society, human beings live together with one another, interact, relate and mingle with one another as a result of which some persons tend to exert influence, dominance or control over others thereby intimidating, harassing and subjugating others. Adopting a combination of physiological approaches, spiced with legal analysis; the paper concludes that the enactment of Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Law by Bauchi State and Plateau State shows commitment by the two states to curb the menace of domestic violence in these states and while the provisions of the law are similar in most of the provisions, there are differences in some other provisions of the law especially with respect to the Shari'a Legal System enforced in Bauchi State. The paper offers some recommendations considered relevant to address the approaches to domestic violence and curbing the menace.

Keywords: Domestic Violence, Relationship, Rape, Victim, Perpetrator, Punishment and Compensation

1. INTRODUCTION

Society and individuals are two inseparable units of human existence. In the course of survival within the society, human beings live together with one another, interact, relate and mingle with one another. This is with a view to providing company, love, support, care, compassion or protection. In the course of this interaction and or living together, human beings tend to exert influence, dominance or control over others thereby intimidating, harassing and subjugating others. Where these intimidation, harassment, maltreatment or abuse takes place as a result of intimate relationship within a premises where the parties are living either in the course of marital relationship or cohabitating together, is referred to as ‘domestic violence’. Domestic violence is interpersonal violence which takes place in domestic settings, family relationship and intimate relationships. It is also known as family violence or spousal abuse¹.

Domestic violence is any destructive behavior in an intimate relationship or cohabitation, which usually causes physical, psychological, emotional or sexual harm to the victim². Domestic violence is usually perpetrated by an intimate partner against the other. It transcends gender, religious and cultural background. The victims of domestic violence include children, teenagers, females, parents, elderly and in some cases adult males.

The principal law prohibiting domestic violence and all other forms of violence is Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Law, which is enacted by most states in Nigeria. Both Bauchi State³ and Plateau State⁴ enacted this law in the year 2022. Although Bauchi State and Plateau State geographically share boundary and have so many common features, the Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Law⁵ enacted by the two states are not entirely the same both in the arrangement of the sections and the substance of the various provisions. This work will compare certain key provisions of the VAPP Law in Bauchi State and Plateau State with a view to identifying the strength and weakness of these laws.

2. MEANING OF DOMESTIC VIOLENCE

¹ See <https://www.ijcwed.com> accessed 4/6/2023

² Abdul Raffie, N “Domestic Violence: Its Causes, Consequences and Precautions Strategies” IJARIE (2016) Vol.2, Issue 2 available at www.ijarie.com accessed 4/6/2023.

³ Bauchi State enacted Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Law, 2022 in the year 2022 and came into operation on the 9th day of December, 2022.

⁴ Plateau State enacted Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Law, 2022 in the year 2022 and came into operation on the 19th day of May, 2022.

⁵ Hereinafter referred to as VAPP Law

Like many concepts, ‘domestic violence’ does not have one single definition that is universally acceptable. Many scholars define the concept according to their understanding. It is defined as any act of violence perpetrated by intimate partners through physical abuse such as slapping, beating, arm twisting, stabbing, strangling, burning, choking, kicking, threats with an object or weapon, and murder, or sexual abuse such as coerced sex through threats, intimidation or physical force, forcing unwanted sexual acts or forcing sex with others; or psychological abuse which includes behavior that is intended to intimidate and persecute, which may take the form of threats of abandonment or abuse, confinement to the home, surveillance, or even threats to take away custody of children, destruction of objects, isolation, verbal aggression and constant humiliation; and/or economic abuse which includes acts such as the denial of funds, refusal to contribute financially, denial of food and basic need and controlling access to health care or employment⁶.

This definition hinges more on the various acts of domestic violence, which is wide enough to accommodate many acts that constitute domestic violence. Domestic violence is often perpetrated by an intimate partner against the other. It cuts across gender and involves violence against children, teenagers, parents or the elderly. It takes the form of physical, verbal, emotional, economic and sexual abuse. It often occurs when the abuser believes that the act is an entitlement, acceptable and justified⁷.

The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW)⁸ defines ‘domestic violence’ against women as any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual and/or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, occurring in private life⁹. This definition is gender specific by restricting the victims of domestic violence to women alone. Although women are naturally weak, in some cases, men are the victims of domestic violence.

⁶ L.B. Dankadai, “Male Dominance and Domestic Violence in Nigeria: An Examination of the Legal Framework for the Protection of Women” *Bayero Journal of Private and Commercial Law (BJPCL)* vol. 1, No.1 page 134

⁷ N. Ezenwugo, “Gender-Based Violence: A Human Rights Violation” National Human Right Commission, Abuja, 23rd March, 2021

⁸ This is an international legal instrument was adopted in 1979 by UN General Assembly. Nigeria ratified CEDAW on 13th June 1985. It requires countries to eliminate discrimination against women and girls in all areas and promotes women’s and girls’ equal right. CEDAW is often described as the international bill of rights for women, and is one of the key international agreements that guide the work of UN Women in achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls.

⁹ See Article 1 and 2 of the Convention.

The VAPP Law of Bauchi State¹⁰ defines ‘domestic violence’ as “*any act perpetrated on any person in a domestic relationship where such act cause harm or may cause imminent harm to the safety, health or wellbeing of any person; forced financial dependence, denial of inheritance or success rights, unreasonable deprivation of economic or financial resources to which a person is entitled or which any person requires out of necessity, including: household necessities, mortgage bond repayment, or payment of rent in respect of a shared residence, reasonable disposal or destruction of household effects or other property in which any person has an interest*”.

As beautiful as this definition appears to be, it only focuses on the commission of an act (active act). The definition has failed to take into account that domestic violence may be perpetrated by the omission or failure to act which failure causes physical or psychological injury to the victim in a domestic relationship.

The VAPP Law of Plateau State¹¹ defines ‘domestic violence’ in almost the same words with that of Bauchi State. It provides thus: “*domestic violence means any act perpetrated on any person in a domestic relationship where such act causes harm or may cause imminent harm to the safety, health or well-being of any person*”. This definition suffers the same deficiency like that of Bauchi State by omitting to take into account the passive act of the perpetrator. Also, the definition under VAPP Law of Bauchi state is more elaborate taking into account economic abuse¹². Thus, domestic violence is any act or omission by the perpetrator on another person who has advantage of influence over the other, in a domestic relationship which such act causes or is capable of causing physical injury or psychological disturbance or financial deprivation and the perpetrator committed such act or omitted to act without any justifiable reason.

3. VIOLENCE AGAINST PERSONS (PROHIBITION) LAW¹³: COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN BAUCHI STATE AND PLATEAU STATE

Bauchi State and Plateau State share boundary with each other. The citizens of these states mingle together and in most cases, share common lineage through inter-marriages. Economically, the economy of the two states depends on one another. Coincidentally, these states enacted their respective VAPP Laws in the same year i.e. year 2022. Notwithstanding

¹⁰ See PART IV, section 34 of Bauchi State VAPP Law, 2022.

¹¹ See section 2 Plateau State VAPP Law, 2022

¹² Economic abuse is separately define by the VAPP Law of Plateau State under same section.

¹³ VAPP Law of Bauchi State, 2022 and VAPP Law of Plateau State, 2022

some of the common features, the two laws are not entirely the same both in substance and structure. Thus, this part of the work will analyze some key provisions of the VAPP Law of Bauchi State and Plateau State with a view to identifying the strength and weakness of these provisions.

i. **Domestic Relationship:** domestic relationship is an essential element in the offence of domestic violence. This is one element that is central in all the definitions of domestic violence. Thus, understanding the meaning and scope of the term ‘domestic relationship’ is necessary in determining the offence of domestic violence. Both VAPP Law of Bauchi State and Plateau State define this concept. Section 2 of Plateau State VAPP Law¹⁴ provides thus:

“ ‘domestic relationship’ means a relationship between any person and a perpetrator of violence constituted in any of the following ways:

- (i) They are or were married to each other, including marriages according to any law, custom or religion;**
- (ii) They live or have lived together in a relationship in the nature of marriage, although they are not or were not married to each other;**
- (iii) They are the parents of a child or children or are the persons who have or had a parental responsibility for that child or children;**
- (iv) They are family members related by consanguinity, affinity or adoption;**
- (v) They are or were in an engagement, dating or customary relationship, including actual or perceived romantic, intimate or sexual relationship of any duration; or**
- (vi) They share or recently shared the same residence;”(*emphasis mine*)**

This definition is elaborate enough to accommodate intimate relationship of all kinds. The section did not only contemplate present relationship but also past relationship of the perpetrator and the victim. The Bauchi State VAPP Law contains similar provision under the interpretation section at Part IV, section 34 of the law. While item (i) to (iv) of the Plateau State

¹⁴ This is the interpretation section of the law. The corresponding section under VAPP Law of Bauchi State is found in PART IV, Section 34 of the Law.

VAPP Law quoted above is replicated at section 34 of Bauchi State VAPP Law, item (v) and (vi) of the above quoted provision are missing in the Bauchi State VAPP Law. It is submitted that item (v) and (vi) of the above quoted section is as important as item (i) to (iv) of the same provision. It is not in doubt that engagement, dating and or romantic relationship are all forms of intimate relationships which domestic violence is liable to take place in the course of such relationship. The same thing with sharing residence, which is common in Nigeria. One wonders why the omission of item (v) and (vi) of the above quoted provisions from the Bauchi State VAPP Law. Perhaps, this may be due to Shari'a legal system enforced in Bauchi State, which prohibits any form of sexual, romantic and any form of intimate relationship with the opposite sex, except within the permissible limit of Islam. Thus, section 2 of the Plateau State VAPP Law is more elaborate than section 34 of Bauchi State VAPP Law.

ii. **Rape:** rape is one of the forms of sexual violence which may be committed as a result of domestic relationship. For instance, during Covid-19 lock down, there was high rate of rape cases committed in a domestic relationship. In Nigeria, it is reported that during the lockdown imposed by the government to arrest the spread of covid-19 in the year 2020, there was upsurge in cases of rape in June, 2020. The Nigerian Police reported that they had recorded 717 cases of rape between January and May that year.¹⁵ In April, 2020, the Nigerian's Minister of Women Affairs, Pauline Tallen stated that at least 3,600 cases of rape were recorded during the lockdown, while the National Human Right Commission received 11,200 reported cases of rape over the whole 2020.¹⁶ These reports clearly show the upsurge in the number of cases of sexual crimes during the covid-19 pandemic. This is not unconnected with the fact that the perpetrators and the victims were indoors as a result of the lockdown.

Part I, section 1 of Bauchi State VAPP Law defines the offence of rape, which definition is the replica of the one under Penal Code Law¹⁷. The only innovation of this section is in Section 1(2)(b) of Bauchi State VAPP Law. The last mentioned section provides thus: **“Penetration is not limited only to penile shaft, but includes penetration by any object including the use of finger(s)”**. No doubt this is an improvement on the traditional definition of rape under the Penal Code as the scope of acts that constitute the offence of rape has been expanded. However, this provision is still deficient and inadequate. Firstly, the provision restricted the objects or

¹⁵ Nigeria: Failure to Tackle Rape crisis Embolden Perpetrators and Silences Survivors available at <https://www.amnesty.org> accessed 21/6/2022.

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ See section 282(1) and (2) of the Penal Code Law

parts of the body used in penetration to only object and finger in addition to penile penetration. Thus, a careful reading of this section will reveal that using tongue (cunnilingus) to penetrate the vagina is not rape since tongue is not an object and the section is specific on the part of the object used to constitute rape. This writer suggests that the said section should be rephrased to include “...**penetration by any object or body part including but not limited to penis, tongue and finger(s)**”. Also, the section is silent on the part of the body to be penetrated upon. The implication of this deficiency is to the effect that it is only the penetration of the vagina by penis, any object or finger that constitutes the offence of rape. Thus, penetration of the victim’s anus, mouth does not constitute rape. Besides, going by this definition, it is only female that can be victim of rape and this is discriminatory against men.

Section 1 of the Bauchi State VAPP Law, does not recognize spousal rape¹⁸. This may not be unconnected with the fact that Bauchi State is predominantly populated by followers of Islamic faith and under Islamic religion, spouses are like garments to each other, meaning each of the spouse has sexual right over the other¹⁹.

Furthermore, Bauchi State VAPP Law uses the phrase ‘sexual intercourse’ in section 1 of the law. Regrettably, the said law fails to define the meaning of sexual intercourse. The interpretation section only defines ‘sexual harassment’, ‘sexual abuse’, ‘sexual assault’, ‘sexual exploitation’ and ‘sexual intimidation’. As to what amount to sexual intercourse as far as that law is concerned, it is left at the mercy of the presiding Judge to interpret. Paragraphs (a) to (e) of the same section only provide instances when the sexual intercourse constitutes rape. This is unlike the Plateau State VAPP Law that avoid using the phrase ‘sexual intercourse’ and clearly state what amounts to rape.

On the other hand, section 3 (1) (a) of the Plateau State VAPP Law provides for a comprehensive definition of rape that is gender neutral. The section provides “**A person commits the offence of rape if: (a) he or she intentionally penetrates the vagina, anus or mouth of another person or with any other part of his/her body or anything else**”²⁰. By this definition, the frontiers of the offence of rape are wide to cover instances where both male and female can commit rape and also the penetration is not restricted to vagina. Penetration of the anus or mouth with any body part or an object can constitute rape. Therefore, the definition

¹⁸ See section 1 (2) (a) of the Bauchi State VAPP Law.

¹⁹ There is implied contract between both spouses at the marriage contract to be submissive to each other’s sexual demand.

²⁰ By this definition, fingering and cunnilingus etc also constitutes rape.

of rape under the Plateau State VAPP Law is more comprehensive, detailed and unambiguous than the provision of section 1 of Bauchi State VAPP Law. The Plateau State Law is silent on the spousal rape unlike the Bauchi State Law that is expressly stated.

iii. **Punishment for rape:** The punishment for rape under Bauchi State and Plateau State VAPP Law is life imprisonment²¹. However, the provision of the Bauchi State Law is more strict, definite and unequivocal by leaving no room for any discretion to the Judge. This we can clearly see by the usage of the word “shall” which generally is interpreted as mandatory²². Thus, a Judge must apply the law as it is and any punishment contrary to the express provision of the law is liable to be set aside on appeal²³. On the other hand, the provision of the law in Plateau State²⁴ appears to give discretion to the Judge on the punishment. The section provides: “A person convicted of an offence under sub section 1 of this section **is liable** to imprisonment for life except...”. The usage of the phrase “is liable” instead of the word ‘shall’ gives the Judge some discretion in the application of the maximum penalty. Thus, some Judges may hide under this provision to impose lesser punishment. It is suggested that given the gravity of the offence of rape and the increase in the cases of rape reported²⁵, the law should be couched in such a way to leave no room for any discretion by the Judge. Thus, the word ‘shall’ should be used instead of the phrase ‘is liable’ as contained in the Bauchi State VAPP Law.

The VAPP Law of Plateau State makes distinction between perpetrator of rape that is under 14 years of age and an adult²⁶. It provides that an offender under 14 years is liable in accordance

²¹ See section 3 of Bauchi State VAPP Law and section 3 (2) of Plateau State VAPP Law.

²² See *Adans v. Umar* (2009) 5 NWLR (Part 1133) 41 CA, the court held inter alia “if a statute provides that a thing “shall” be done, the expected and proper meaning is that a peremptory and absolute mandate is enjoined...”. Also in *Nwankwo v. Yaradua* (2013) 13 NWLR (Part 1263) 81 CA where the court held thus: “The use of the word “shall” in a statute or rules of court makes it mandatory that the rule or provision must be observed...”. See also the following cases *Onochie v. Odohwu* (2006) 6 NWLR (Part 975) 65; *Afolabi v. Gov. Oyo State* (1985)2 NWLR (Part 91) 734.

²³ See *Akpan v. State* (1994) 8 NWLR (Part 361)226 CA, the court held: “A judge is not the law maker and so he must apply the law in its present form”. In *Onyeausi v. Misc. Offences Tribunal* (1995) 8 NWLR (Part 415) 628 CA, the court held thus: “where the words of a statute are clear and unambiguous, the court must give effect to them and they will override the intention of the law maker...”. Also in *Maida v. Modu* (2000) 4 NWLR (Part 651) 99, it was held “courts are to interpret and apply the law as it is not as it ought to be”.

²⁴ See Section 3 (2) of Plateau State VAPP Law

²⁵ For instance, it is reported that a total number of 91 cases of rape were recorded between January and February in Lagos, said the Lagos State Commissioner of police. See *Adediran Ifeoluwa* “Lagos Records 91 Rape Cases in Two Months”. Premium Times, March 23, 2021 available at <https://www.premiumtimesng.com> accessed 21/6/2022.

²⁶ Rape is not only omitted by adults. Premium times earlier reported how four teenagers gang-raped a girl at the Ejigbo area of Lagos. The suspects all 6 years old, raped the girl in a room at No. 33 Alhaji Obe Street, Ejigbo, around 10pm on February. See Premium Times, March 23, 2021 available at <https://www.premiumtimesng.com> accessed 21/6/2022.

with Child Right Law of Plateau State, 2005²⁷. There is no similar provision under the Bauchi State VAPP Law. Perhaps, they may be due to the fact that Bauchi State is yet to enact Child Right Law. But the Bauchi State VAPP Law provides special protection of the child victim of rape by specifically providing for a stiffer punishment for child rape. Section 3 (c)²⁸ provides: “*A person who has carnal knowledge of a minor shall upon conviction be sentence to death by hanging*”²⁹. Perhaps this is the severest punishment under the law and the law makers did not leave any stone unturned by using the word ‘shall’ in the provision. No doubt, this is a welcome development especially at a time like this, where minors and in some cases even infants are brutally raped³⁰. This punishment if applied will serve as deterrence to rapists. The Plateau State Law does not have similar provision.

iv. **Gang rape:** Rape by group of persons is gang rape³¹ and same is punishable with minimum imprisonment of 20 years without option of fine. This punishment is the same under both laws³². It is ironical that punishment for gang rape, which is severe and more dangerous on the victim, is milder than the punishment for rape by single individual (which is life imprisonment). The punishment for group or gang rape should be more severe. It is suggested that gang rape should be punished with death sentence.

v. **Medical report:** section 2 (a) of Bauchi State VAPP Law renders medical report in rape cases immaterial and insignificant. The section provides “*when a court is trying the offence of rape, medical report shall be immaterial*”. This provision is unique to Bauchi State VAPP Law. One cannot fathom the rationale behind this provision of the law. Perhaps, this section is inserted to lessen the burden of proof on the prosecuting authority. Further, the section used the word “shall” which suggests mandatory compliance. But can the law makers stop a party who is willing to tender medical evidence at a trial? The implication of the word “shall” used in the provision is to render medical report in all cases of rape immaterial. What about if in the circumstances of a particular case, medical report is necessary to establish the guilt of the defendant? It is important to note that facts of cases determine the relevant evidence whether oral or documentary. More so, where the victim is taken for medical examination, then the medical report of that examination has become relevant. Besides, relevancy determines the

²⁷ See section 3 (2) (a) Plateau State VAPP Law.

²⁸ See Bauchi State VAPP Law.

²⁹ Section 34 of Bauchi State VAPP Law defines minor as a child below the age of 14 years.

³⁰ See Premium Times, March 23, 2021 available at <https://www.premiumtimesng.com> accessed 21/6/2022.

³¹ See section 3 (3) Plateau State VAPP Law

³² See section 1 (3) (b) of Bauchi State VAPP Law.

admissibility of an evidence³³. It is suggested that the word “may” shall be use to replace “shall” in the said provision. This is with a view to giving discretion to whoever wishes to tender medical report to do so and also it is for the court to determine how material a medical report is to the case. Thus, it is not the responsibility of the law makers to determine whether a document is material or not³⁴. The law should be flexible to accommodate variety of circumstances.

vi. **Compensation:** payment of compensation is one of the beautiful innovations of VAPP Law of Plateau State and Bauchi State³⁵. Section 3 (4) of Plateau State VAPP Law provides thus: **“The court shall also award appropriate compensation to the victim as it may deem fit in the circumstance”**. This provision gives the Judge the discretion to determine the appropriate compensation payable to the victim of rape. Therefore, in determining the compensation, the facts and circumstances of each case will be taken into consideration. For instance, the court shall take into account the medical expenses incurred by the victim, the loss of earnings suffered by the victim, the damage caused to the victim’s health. For instance, a victim infected with HIV/AIDS by the rapist, deserves handsome amount of compensation. As beautiful as this innovation is, the practicability of the section in Nigeria is challenging. Firstly, the section is silent as to who will pay the compensation to the victim. Is it the convict or the Government? Secondly, at what point shall the compensation be paid to the victim? Is it before, during or after the trial? Thirdly, is the victim entitled to this compensation even when the defendant is discharged and acquitted, since the victim has been raped although not approved against the defendant? All these questions beg for rational answers since the provision of the law is not clear.

Since there has never been a time when government pay compensation to a victim of crime in Nigeria, it is assumed that this compensation is to be paid by the defendant. How will the defendant pay this compensation is another problem especially considering the fact that he will be sentenced to not less than 20 years imprisonment and without option of fine? Certainly the defendant if convicted will not pay any compensation to the victim even if he/she has the means

³³ *Akubo v. Nigerian Army (2022) 1 NWLR (Part 1811) 377 SC*. The court held that “the hallmark of admissibility is relevancy...”; *Hamza v. State (2019) 16 NWLR (Part 1699) 418 SC* “Admissibility, one of the cornerstones of the Law of Evidence, is based on relevancy...”. See also *Abubakar v. Chuks (2007) 18 NWLR (Part 1066) 386 SC*.

³⁴ It is the duty of the court, who is faced with the facts of the case, to determine how material or otherwise a medical report.

³⁵ Prior to enactment of these law, there was no provision of the law that makes specific provision for the payment of compensation to the victim of rape.

to pay. It is suggested that a department in the judiciary should be created and saddled with the mandate of enforcing the compensation even if the defendant is in custody at the correctional centre. Compensation payable by the defendant shall be paid at the end of the trial, after conviction. But if the compensation is to be paid by the government, it is suggested that it should be paid immediately it is confirmed that the victim has been raped. This will help the victim to take care of medical bills and will encourage the victim psychologically to move on with life.

Section 16 of the Bauchi State VAPP Law makes provision for the payment of compensation by any person convicted of any offence under the law. Unlike the Plateau State law, this section is not specific to offence of rape. However, unlike compensation under Plateau State law, compensation under section 16 of the Bauchi State law may be awarded either in addition to or in substitution of any other punishment. Thus, section 16 of Bauchi State VAPP Law is clear on who will pay the compensation. The section reads: **“A person who is convicted of an offence under this law may be adjudged to make compensation to any person injured by his offence...”**. Thus, the convict shall pay the compensation to the victim. Unlike the Plateau State VAPP Law, section 16 which did not make it clear that the compensation shall be ‘appropriate’.

4. CONCLUSION

The enactment of Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Law by Bauchi State and Plateau State shows commitment by the two states to curb the menace of domestic violence in these states. The provisions of the laws are apt and address many challenges of domestic violence. This research compares the provisions of VAPP Law of Bauchi State and Plateau State and it reveals the areas of similarities and differences aimed at addressing domestic violence and promoting social justice. Both states prioritize victim protection and offender accountability. While the provisions of the law are similar in most of the provisions, there are differences in some other provisions of the law. Plateau State Law demonstrates robust approach with comprehensive provisions covering various forms of violence, Bauchi State Law is influenced by cultural and religious background of the community. The research finds that the two laws are deficient in some in some provisions, leaving gaps and ambiguity in interpreting those provisions of the law. Also, the two states have many provisions to copy from one another in order to improve the laws and effectively address the challenges of domestic violence.

Based on the above analysis, this paper finds as follows:

1. The definition of rape under section 1 of the Bauchi State Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Law is vague, deficient, discriminatory against male gender and not in line with the modern definition of rape.
2. Section 3 of Plateau State Violence against Persons (Prohibition) Law which provides punishment for rape couched in such a way as to give a Judge some discretion by using the phrase “is liable” unlike the Bauchi State Law which uses the word “shall”.
3. Bauchi State VAPP Law contains a unique provision in section 2 (a) of the law which exclude the requirement of medical report at the trial in rape case, which section may be in conflict with relevant provisions of the Evidence Act on relevancy and admissibility and documentary evidence.
4. Section 3 (4) of the Plateau State law which provides for the payment of compensation to the victim of rape did not expressly mention who will pay the compensation unlike the relevant provision of the Bauchi State Law.

Flowing from the above findings, this paper makes the following recommendations:

- i. Section 1 of the Bauchi State VAPP Law be amended and same should be redrafted to accommodate various instances when rape will be committed like the penetration of tongue and other body parts to penetrate not only the vagina but the mouth and anus of the victim.
- ii. Section 3 of the Plateau State VAPP Law should be amended and the phrase “is liable” should be replace with the word “shall” in order to foreclose the possibility of imposing lesser term of imprisonment.
- iii. Section 2 of Bauchi State VAPP Law should also be amended and redrafted by replacing the word “shall” with the word “may”. This will make the provision flexible and avoid conflict with the relevant provisions of the Evidence Act.
- iv. Section 3 (4) of Plateau State VAPP Law should be amended and couched to expressly mention the person or authority to pay the compensation and how to

enforce the compensation where the convict is serving his term at the correctional centre.